

THE STRENGTHENING MECHANISMS OF
DISCONTINUOUS METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The addition of discontinuous silicon carbide (SiC) to aluminum (Al) alloys can result in a five-fold increase in the yield stress. The magnitude of the increase is obviously a function of the volume fraction and the particle size of the SiC. Previously, it was proposed that the strength increase due to SiC addition to Al alloys was the result of change in the matrix strength, i.e., an increase in dislocation density and a reduction of subgrain size. The data obtained from a series of experiments indicate that dislocation density increases with an increase in volume fraction of SiC and decreases with an increase in particle size. The subgrain size decreases as the volume fraction increases and increases as the particle size increases. Overall, there is good agreement between the microstructure (dislocation density) change and the macroscale deformation of SiC/Al composite tensile samples. The mechanism proposed to account for this change in deformation behavior as a function of volume fraction of SiC in Al is related to the expansion of the plastic zone (due to differences in thermal coefficients of expansion between SiC and Al) when the external stress is applied. There is good correlation between the microstructural changes in the matrix and the changes in the yield stress of the composites. Also, the localized deformation is related to localized clusters of SiC particles. There is a cooperative effect which leads to a region of very localized plastic deformation.

KEYWORDS: Particulate composite, strengthening mechanism, dislocation density, electron microscopy, deformation

1. INTRODUCTION

The classical composite strengthening theories (1-5) have been applied to discontinuous metal matrix composites, but these theories are not capable of accounting for the observed strengthening. The concept of strengthening due to an increase in dislocation density has been in existence for several decades, probably since shortly after the original proposal of edge dislocations by Orwan, Polyani and Taylor (6). Over the subsequent years, there have been numerous investigations which have correlated a strength increase with an increase in dislocation density. The strengthening due to a reduction in subgrain size is not as old as the concept of strengthening due to an increase in the dislocation density (7). However, the correlation has been demonstrated quite clearly by several individuals; in particular by McQueen et al. (8).

It was first proposed by Arsenault (9) a few years ago that the strengthening of Al and Al alloys due to the addition of discontinuous SiC reinforcements occurred as a result of generation of dislocations which produced an increase in dislocation density and a reduced subgrain size in the matrix. The generation is due to a difference in thermal coefficient of expansion between the matrix and the reinforcement (ΔCTE). The presence of the high dislocation density within the matrix has been demonstrated along with a very small subgrain size. An in situ investigation has demonstrated the validity of the ΔCTE mechanisms as a means by which the high dislocation density is produced within the matrix (10). Further, it has been shown that a very simple model based on prismatic punching is capable of producing an adequate dislocation density (11). However, it should be clearly pointed out that this model will only predict the lower limit of the dislocation density. Attempts to calculate the upper limit of the dislocation density due to the ΔCTE effect have proven unsuccessful, for all of the calculations predicted a very high dislocation density, i.e., approaching infinity, which obviously is not correct.

However, several questions remain pertaining to the details of the strengthening mechanism of discontinuously reinforced metal matrix composites based on the strengthening of the matrix due to a change in the microstructure of the matrix. The first question is related to transmission electron microscopy (TEM) procedures for determining dislocation densities; a) Does the sample preparation technique, i.e. dimpling and ion milling, introduce damage into the TEM foil? and b) If a thin region of the foil is examined (i.e., the viewing region) at 100-200 KV, will a lower dislocation density be observed? In regard to part b of the above question, there have been a few investigations which have determined the dislocation density as a function of foil thickness and the most recent are by Fajita et al. (12-14). In the case of pure Al, it was found that the foil thickness had to be greater than 1 μm to obtain a bulk dislocation density. The question arises, since SiC/Al is not high purity Al, does this requirement of foil thickness still apply? The second question: Is there an overall relationship between dislocation density (ρ), subgrain size (λ), reinforcement particle size (D) and

volume fraction (V), and the increase in the yield stress of the composite? There have been several investigations where the dislocation density was determined for a specific particle size and volume fraction, but there have been no systematic investigations of these parameters. Also, there are no systematic investigations of the subgrain size as a function of particle size and volume fraction. The third question: Is it possible to increase the strength of the matrix sufficiently to account for the strengthening? In other words, if the Al matrix alone (with no SiC present) had the same dislocation density as in the composite, would the Al matrix have the same strength as the composite? Is it possible to increase the dislocation density and reduce the subgrain size within the Al alloy matrix by cold working to approach the yield strength of a composite containing 20 V% reinforcement in the same Al alloy matrix? Another question: The deformation of discontinuous metal matrix composites appears to be very localized as observed in previous investigations (9). The question is why the deformation is localized. An investigation was undertaken to address the questions raised above.

2. Materials and Testing

2.1 Composite Materials All of the composite materials were produced by a powder metallurgical procedure. The Al alloy powders were mixed with particulate or whisker SiC, hot-compacted and hot-extruded into 12.7 mm diameter rods or hot pressed into a plate. The 0, 5 and 20 V% SiC whiskers/6061 Al alloy composites plus the 0 V%/1100 Al alloy composites were purchased from ARCO SILAG*. The 20 V% SiC-250 μm particulate/1100 Al alloy composite was purchased from DWA** in the form of a plate. The remainder of the material was produced in the Metallurgical Materials Laboratory of the University of Maryland in the form of an extruded rod. From the extruded rod and plate, tensile samples were machined into a configuration as described elsewhere (9). Prior to tensile testing, the samples were annealed for 12 hours at 803 K and furnace cooled. Those that were to be heat treated were given a modified T6 heat treatment, which means a solutionizing step of three hours (modified) as opposed to the standard one hour. All of the tensile testing was conducted at room temperature at a strain rate of 10^{-4} sec^{-1} . The procedure for thinning the TEM foils and the method of determining the dislocation densities is given elsewhere (10). The electron microscopy investigation involved the use of two microscopes, a JEOL 100 CX operating at 100 KV and the Argonne National Laboratory modified Kratos/AEI EM7 HVEM operated at 1 MV.

2.2 Cold Rolled 0 V% 1100 Al Alloy The cold rolled strips were produced by taking 0 V% 1100 Al alloy material purchased from ARCO Silag and rolling without any intermediate annealing until a reduction in thickness of $\sim 90\%$ was obtained. The

* Now, Advanced Composite Materials of Greer, South Carolina.

** Composite Specialties of Chatsworth, California.

tensile sample preparation and testing were the same as described in the preceding section on composite materials. This also applies to the TEM foil preparation and examination.

2.3 High Purity Al Relatively high purity Al (99.99%) was obtained in the form of a rod, 12.7 mm dia. from ALCOA as a gift. This material was annealed for 12 hours at 803 K and furnace cooled. The TEM foils of high purity Al were produced by two different procedures. Some of the foils were produced by using the same method as used for composite foils. The other samples, after being cut into 0.5 mm thick disks by electrical discharge machining, were electrochemically thinned using a jet polishing device. The foils were examined at 100 KV and 1 MV.

Melted 250 μm particulate reinforced composite material was chosen for optical observation of slip lines. Rectangular samples 8 mm wide by 50 mm long and 1.5 mm thick were electrical-discharged-machined and polished. The samples were glued to a E. Fullam tensile substage model No. 18202 JEOL JSM-35. The substage was mounted onto a specially constructed holder to fit on to a Zeiss ICM-405. The entire effective gauge was photographed. Then the sample was deformed a small amount and the area which contained slip lines was re-photographed, and again the sample was deformed and re-photographed where slip lines occurred. This process was repeated until the sample fractured. The method of producing the "melted" SiC/Al composites is described elsewhere (15).

3. RESULTS

3.1 Yield Strength Of interest is the incremental increase in the yield stress (which is defined as the stress at a plastic strain of 0.2%) due to the addition of the reinforcement. Therefore, the yield stress of the 0 V% matrix alloy is subtracted from the yield stress of the composite. The incremental yield stress ($\Delta\sigma_y$) is what is plotted and listed in all cases. As expected, as the size of the SiC particulate increased, the strength decreased, as shown in Fig. 1. The squares represent the average of at least three tests and there could be as many as ten tests for a given particulate size. The arrow bars define the range of scatter. The ultimate strength is only slightly larger than the yield strength indicating that the work hardening rate past yielding is small. The uniform strain was fairly constant, between 3 and 4% for the 0.5 to 9 μm composite materials, then increasing to 6-7% uniform strain for the 20 and 70 μm particulate and slightly larger on average for the 250 μm particulate size composites. Increasing the volume fraction of SiC resulted in an increase in strength (Fig. 2), but not linearly as predicted by the classical-continuum-load transfer-shear lag model, which is indicated by the dashed line in Fig. 2.

MML 194

Fig. 1 The change in the yield stress as a function of SiC/particulate size. The matrix is a 1100 Al alloy. The composite is in the annealed condition.

MML 77

Fig. 2 The change in the yield stress as a Function of the volume fraction of SiC (SiC whisker is $\sim 0.5 \mu\text{m}$ in dia.). The matrix is a 6061 alloy. The composites is in the annealed condition. The shear lag model is described elsewhere (Ref. 16).

Fig. 3(a) A transmission electron micrograph taken at an operating voltage of 100 KV.

Fig. 3(b) A transmission electron micrograph taken at an operating voltage of 100 KV. This micrograph is of the enclosed area in Fig. 3(a).

Fig. 3(c) A transmission electron micrograph taken at an operating voltage of 1 MV.

Fig. 3(d) A transmission electron micrograph taken at an operating voltage of 1 MV. This micrograph is of the enclosed area in Fig. 3(c).

3.2 Dislocation Density Determinations The first investigation involved preparing TEM foils from annealed and furnace cooled high purity Al rods by two different procedures as described in 2.3. The dislocation densities are low in both cases. It is confirmed that the dimpling and ion milling do not introduce any detectable increase in the dislocation density.

The second investigation was related to foil thickness (viewing thickness) as related to dislocation density. If the operating voltage of the TEM is 100 KV, the thickness of the foil in which dislocations may be viewed is 0.2 to 0.4 μm . However, if the operating voltage is 1 MV, the thickness of the foil increases to 1 to 2 μm . If we consider the micrograph shown in Fig. 3, we can see the effect of foil thickness on the dislocation densities. Figures 3(a) and (b) are micrographs taken at 100 KV and the foil thickness in Fig. 3(b) in which a few dislocations are visible is 0.3 μm and the dislocation density is $1.6 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$. Fig. 3(c) and (d) are micrographs taken at an operating voltage of 1 MV. The dislocation density in Fig. 3(d) is $4.5 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$ and the foil thickness is 0.9 μm . Figures 3 (a), (b), (c) and (d) are micrographs taken from the same area of a foil under the same operating diffraction condition, only a thinner area around the brim of the hole is transparent for the 100 KV microscope. This is a general result for all composites examined. If a low operating voltage is used, i.e. 100-200 KV, the apparent dislocation density is low compared to the dislocation density obtained from foils examined at 1 MV. Therefore, in order to obtain realistic measures of dislocation density, it is necessary to examine thinner foils which need an operating voltage (800 KV to 1 MV).

TABLE I

Comparison of 9 μ m Particle Size 20 V% SiC/Al Composite with Cold Rolled 0 V% 1100 Al Composite

Material	Dislocation Density $\rho \times 10^{14} \text{ m}^{-2}$	Subgrain Size $\lambda \times \mu\text{m}$	Δ Experimental Yield Stress $\Delta\sigma_{y_{0.2}} \%$ MPa
20 V% SiC _p	1.1	2	88
0 V% CR	.15	2	116

Δ experimental yield stress = the yield stress of the composite minus the yield stress of 0 V% matrix.

condition (i.e. particle size or volume fraction) in Figs. 4 and 5 represent tens to hundreds of micrographs of a given foil and 5-6 different foils were examined for each condition. The dislocation densities reported are the average dislocation densities in the matrix of annealed samples.

3.3. Effect of Cold Rolling The cold rolling reduced the subgrain size slightly from 5-10 μm to 2 μm , but there was a significant increase in dislocation from less than 10^{10} m^{-2} to $1.5 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$. The cold rolling increased the yield strength from 30 MPa to 146 MPa. If a comparison is made with the 9 μm SiC particle size in 20 V% 1100 Al alloy matrix composite, it can be seen that the $\Delta\sigma_y$ is greater for the cold rolling material than that of the SiC_p/1100 Al alloy composite (Table I). However, the interesting point is that the dislocation density in the composite is much greater than that of the 0 V% 1100 Al alloy cold rolled material.

3.4 Dislocation Density Vs. Distance As shown in Figs. 6, 7 and 8, a high dislocation density is restricted to the vicinity of the fracture surface which represents the highest plastic deformation site for the composites. The higher the volume fraction of the SiC, the more concentrated the localized deformation.

3.5 Slip line analysis The initial slip lines began in a region which contained a higher than average density of SiC particles (that is, a cluster). The very first slip lines which occur in this higher density of SiC particle region, occur at the corners of SiC particles. Slip lines were observed at the corners of other SiC particles through the gauge length of the sample. The region with the higher than average density of SiC particles contain almost all the subsequent increase in slip line density. In other areas

Upon increasing the volume fraction, the dislocation density increases, but upon increasing the volume fraction, the subgrain size decreases as shown in Fig. 4, and upon increasing the particle size, the opposite is the case, the dislocation density decreases (and the subgrain size increases) as the particle size increases (Fig. 5). The data given for each

TABLE 2

**Predicted Increase in Yield Strength of 20 V% SiC 1100
Matrix and Experimentally Measured Values**

Particle Size D (μm)	$\Delta\sigma_{\rho}$ MPa	$\Delta\sigma_{\text{SG}}$ MPa	$\Delta\sigma_{\text{res}}$ MPa	$\Delta\sigma_{\text{Ypred}}$ MPa	$\Delta\sigma_{\text{Yexp}}$ MPa
0.5	126.6	131	17	240.6	153
9	99	69	17	151	88
70	79	20	17	82	69
250	59.7	0-13.8	17	42.7-56.5	26

Key

$\Delta\sigma_{\text{Yexp}}$ The yield stress defined at 0.2% plastic strain minus the 0.2% yield stress of the 0 V% 1100 matrix

$\Delta\sigma_{\rho}$ The predicted increase due to the increased dislocation density

$\Delta\sigma_{\text{SG}}$ The predicted increase due to the reduced sub-grain size

$\Delta\sigma_{\text{res}}$ The predicted average tensile residual stress

$\Delta\sigma_{\text{Ypred}}$ The sum of $\Delta\sigma_{\rho} + \Delta\sigma_{\text{SG}} - \Delta\sigma_{\text{res}}$

of the sample there are no or very few slip lines [17].

4. DISCUSSION

The discussion will follow along the lines of the questions raised in the Introduction.

4.1 Dislocation and Subgrain Size Determinations The outcome of this investigation is that the dimpling and ion milling *DO NOT* introduce any dislocations into the TEM foil. In regard to the question raised concerning the viewing thickness of the TEM foil, besides the image force which is still present, there are other factors which contribute to the loss of dislocations from the thinned foil. There are thermal residual stresses within the SiC/Al alloy composite prior to thinning. If we consider the points labeled 1 and 2 in Fig. 9, there is a tensile residual stress acting in the direction A-A', B-B', C-C' and D-D'. If the sample is cut along the lines A-A' and B-B', the stress at the surfaces will have to relax to zero. A simple manner of stress relaxation is by dislocation motion out of the foil. For a thinner foil, there will be a larger fraction of dislocations lost from the sample. Therefore, in order to obtain reasonable measures of the

Fig. 4 The change in dislocation density and subgrain size as a function of volume fraction of particulate.

Fig. 5 The change in dislocation density and subgrain size as a function of particulate size.

dislocation density, it is necessary to examine thicker portions of the TEM foil, which means examining the foil at 1 MEV. The determination of the subgrain size is not as dependent on the foil thickness or the foil preparation procedure.

4.2 Correlation Between Microstructural Changes And Yield Stress The increase in the yield stress with an increase in the volume fraction or the decrease of yield stress with an increase in the particle size is to be expected. Correspondingly, the dislocation density and the subgrain change in the expected manner. However, it is necessary to consider if *THE CHANGES IN THE YIELD STRESS CAN BE RELATED TO THE CHANGES IN DISLOCATION DENSITY AND THE SUBGRAIN SIZE*.

Before considering these correlations, it is necessary to point out that very little global plastic strain is occurring between the proportional limit and the defined yield stress. Therefore, an assumption is made that the *average* increase in the dislocation density is small due to the initial loading to a plastic strain of 0.2%, and that the stress field which opposes dislocation motion at a strain of 0.2% is due to the average dislocation density

Fig. 6 Dislocation density vs. distance from fracture surface for 20 V% SiC/Al composite.

Fig. 7 Dislocation density vs. distance from fracture surface for 5 V% SiC/Al composite.

of the annealed undeformed formed sample. Therefore, we can use the well-established relationship, $\Delta\sigma_y = \alpha\mu b\sqrt{\rho}$ where $\Delta\sigma_y$ is the increase in the yield stress of the composite over that of the 0 V% matrix material, α is a constant and Hansen (18) has shown that for Al, it is 1.25, μ is the shear modulus of the matrix (2.64×10^4 MPa), b is the Burgers vector (2.86×10^{-10} m) and ρ is the dislocation density. In terms of strengthening due to a reduction in subgrain size, it is necessary to rely on the data of McQueen (8). In Tables II and III are listed the predicted increase in strength due to a reduction in the subgrain size $\Delta\sigma_{SG}$ and an increase in dislocation density and the increase in strength due to the reduction in subgrain size becomes predominant at 20 V%. In Table II are listed the incremental increases in the strength due to an increase in dislocation density as a function of changes in particle size at a constant volume fraction of 20%. The incremental increase in strength is large for the case 0.5 μm particle size, and decreases as the particle size increases. In the larger particle size range, the predicted incremental increase in strength due to the increased dislocation

Fig. 8 Dislocation density vs. distance from fracture surface for 0 V% SiC/Al composite.

Fig. 9 A schematic arrangement of SiC whiskers and platelets with arbitrary thinning to a TEM foil.

density alone exceeds the increase in the experimental yield stress.

Although the increase in the dislocation density and the decrease in subgrain size are the major factors affecting the strength change of the matrix, there are other possible contributions to the strength change of the matrix (19). It is obvious that the strengthening includes residual stresses, differences in texture between the composite matrix and the matrix material without reinforcement, classical composite strengthening (i.e. load transfer) and dispersion strengthening. The average residual stress is the only factor which has to be considered; the other factors are very small or zero. The residual stress in the matrix is in tension (20) it would be a negative contribution to strengthening of the composite. The values in Tables II and III are from the analytical predictions of Arsenault and Taya (20).

In general, the predicted increase in the yield strength is much larger than the experimentally determined yield strength. There are at least two possible explanations for this discrepancy. The first possibility is that the value taken for the constant α in Eq. 1 is too large. The values reported in the literature for α range from 0.5 to 1.25. The

second possibility is that the assumption of using an average dislocation density is not valid for the plastic strain at 0.2% and may be due to the motion of dislocations in the matrix where the dislocation density is much lower than the average density. This certainly could account for the discrepancy in the 250 μm particle size composite and the 1 V% composite where the variation in the dislocation density is the greatest.

4.3 Strengthening of the Matrix The cold rolled investigation has shown that the 0 V% 1100 Al alloy material can have a yield stress which is comparable in strength to a 20 V% SiC/Al alloy composite.

4.4 Localized Deformation The evidence obtained from the dislocation density and the slip line investigations is overwhelming: deformation in the higher volume fraction composites is very localized. From an analysis of the configuration of SiC particles in the samples which were used for the slip line analysis, it is evident that the slip lines began in regions which contained a clustering of SiC particles. The slip propagated from one cluster region to another and deformation in the remainder of the samples is almost zero. The phenomenon of localized deformation was duplicated by a FEM analysis.

TABLE 3

Predicted Increase in Yield Stress of 6061/Al Alloy
as a Function of Volume Fraction of SiC Whisker

Volume V%	$\Delta\sigma_{\rho}$ MPa	$\Delta\sigma_{SG}$ MPa	$\Delta\sigma_{res}$ MPa	$\Delta\sigma_{ypred}$ MPa	$\Delta\sigma_{yexp}$ MPa
1	37.7	0.0	1.7	36.0	6.9
5	56.6	7.0	8.6	55.0	52.0
20	70.0	48.3	34.5	83.8	100.0

Key $\Delta\sigma_{yexp}$	The yield stress defined at 0.2% plastic strain minus the 0.2% yield stress of the 0 V% 1100 matrix
$\Delta\sigma_{\rho}$	The predicted increase due to the increased dislocation density
$\Delta\sigma_{SG}$	The predicted increase due to the reduced sub-grain size
$\Delta\sigma_{res}$	The predicted average tensile residual stress
$\Delta\sigma_{ypred}$	The sum of $\Delta\sigma_{\rho} + \Delta\sigma_{SG} - \Delta\sigma_{res}$

5. CONCLUSIONS

From a consideration of the data, several conclusions were obtained:

- The observed strength of the discontinuous SiC/Al composite can be accounted for in terms of a mechanism based on a change in the microstructure of the matrix. Arsenault was the first to point out that these microstructural changes were due to the difference in thermal coefficient of expansion between the reinforcement and the matrix.
- This change in the microstructure, i.e. an increased dislocation

density and a reduced subgrain size as compared to 0 V% matrix alloy, is due to the difference in coefficient of expansion between the reinforcement (SiC) and the matrix (Al).

- The procedure of TEM foil preparation of the composites which involves electrical discharge machining, dimpling and ion milling does not introduce dislocations into the matrix.
- In order to obtain realistic values of the dislocation density, it is necessary to view thick foils, i.e. an operating voltage of 1 MV.
- In discontinuous metal matrix composites containing a high volume fraction of particles and whiskers, the deformation is highly localized. There are three distinct manifestations of localized deformations: (1) There are very narrow "necks" in fracture samples, (2) The high dislocation density is confined to a small region very close to the fracture surface, and (3) The slip line generation is confined to a localized region.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was supported by the Office of Naval Research under contract No. N00014-K-85-0007. The positive interactions with Dr. S. Fishman of that office are greatly acknowledged. The authors also wish to acknowledge the continued support of the Argonne National Laboratory HVEM facility, especially that of Dr. E. Ryan.

7. REFERENCES

1. K.K. Chawla, Composite Materials: Science and Engineering, (New York, NY, Springer-Verlag, 1987).
2. D. Hull, An Introduction to Composite Materials, (Cambridge, U.K., Cambridge University, 1981).
3. A. Kelly, Strong Solids, 2nd. ed. (Clarendon Press, Oxford, U.K., 1973).
4. M.R. Piggott, Load-Bearing Fibre Composites (Pergamon Press, Oxford, U.K., 1980).
5. V. Nardone, Scripta Metall., 21 (1987), 1313.
6. G.I. Taylor, Proc. Roy. Soc. A 145 (1934) 362, J. Inst. Met. 62 (1938) 307.
7. G. Boas, Helv. Phys. Acta 23 (1950) 159.
8. H.J. McQueen and J.E. Hackett, Metal. Trans. 1 (1970) 2997.
9. R.J. Arsenault, Mater. Sci. Eng. 64 (1984) 171.
10. M. Vogelsang, R. Fisher and R.J. Arsenault, Metal. Trans. 17A (1986) 379.
11. R.J. Arsenault and N. Shi, Mater. Sci. Eng. 81 (1986) 175.
12. H. Fujita, Y. Kawasali, E. Furubayashi, Japan J. Appl. Phys. 6 (1967) 214.
13. H. Fujita, T. Tabata, K. Yoshida, N. Summida and S. Katagiri, Japan J. Appl. Phys. 11 (1972) 1522.
14. H. Fujita, T. Tabata, Japan J. Appl. Phys. 12 (1973) 471.
15. R.J. Arsenault and S.B. Wu, Scripta Metall. 22 (1988) 762.
16. M. Taya and R.J. Arsenault, Scripta Metall. 21 (1987) 349.
17. R.J. Arsenault, N. Shi, L. Wang and C.R. Feng, Mater. Sci. Eng. A131 (1991) 55.
18. N. Hansen, Acta Metal. 25 (1977) 863.
19. R.J. Arsenault, J. Comp. Tech. & Res. 10 (1988) 140.
20. R.J. Arsenault and M. Taya, Acta Metall. 35 (1987) 651.

